

SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINS FROM *o*-HYDROXY-ARYL ALKYL KETONES. PART IV. FORMATION OF *o*-COUMARIC ACIDS FROM *o*-HYDROXY-ALDEHYDES

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2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde, 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and 2-naphthol methyl ether-1-aldehyde have been condensed under Reformatsky's condition with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl α -bromopropionate to give hydroxy-esters, which on dehydration and hydrolysis yield *trans*-acids (*o*-coumaric acids). It has been shown that *o*-methoxy-aldehydes always lead to *trans*-*o*-methoxycinnamic acids by Perkin's reaction, by Chakravarti and Majumdar's method and by malonic acid condensation.

The *o*-hydroxy-aryl alkyl ketones have been conveniently used by Chakravarti *et al* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 136; 1940, 17, 65) for the synthesis of coumarin derivatives.

In attempting to synthesise coumarin derivatives by this method, Chakravarti and Majumdar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 389) have observed that when *o*-hydroxy-aldehydes are condensed with ethyl bromoacetate or ethyl α -bromopropionate *trans*-cinnamic esters are formed, which do not yield coumarins on heating with hydriodic acid or on keeping with concentrated sulphuric acid in the cold as in the case of the cinnamic esters, obtained from *o*-hydroxy-aryl alkyl ketones.

The present investigation has been undertaken to study the general applicability of this method for the synthesis of *o*-coumaric acids by the condensation of the methoxy-aldehydes with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl α -bromopropionate and subsequent dehydration and hydrolysis and to note the influence of any group in the phenyl nucleus on the formation of *o*-coumaric acids.

The following condensations have been studied and the products in each case have been found to be *trans*-cinnamic esters, which resist all attempts for lactonisation to coumarins.

Aldehyde.	Halogenated fatty ester.	Product.
2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde	Ethyl bromoacetate	2-Methoxy-5-methyl- <i>trans</i> -cinnamic acid
,,	Ethyl α -bromopropionate	2-Methoxy-5-methyl- <i>trans</i> - α -methylcinnamic acid
2:4-Dimethoxy-benzaldehyde	Ethyl α -bromopropionate	2:4-Dimethoxy- <i>trans</i> - α -methylcinnamic acid
2-Naphthol methyl ether-1-aldehyde	Ethyl bromoacetate	β -(2-Methoxy)-1-naphthylacrylic acid
,,	Ethyl α -bromopropionate	β -(2-Methoxy)-1-naphthyl- α -methylacrylic acid

The study of the condensation of 2-methoxy-aldehydes with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl α -bromopropionate shows that the method of Chakravarti and Majumdar for the synthesis of *o*-coumaric acid seems to be a very general method as it is found that *trans*-esters are invariably formed if there is no β -alkyl substituent in the expected cinnamic ester.

A reference to literature shows that the methoxylated *o*-coumaric acids, prepared by this method, are identical with the *o*-methoxycinnamic acids, prepared by Perkin's reaction on 2-methoxy-aldehydes, *e.g.*, 2:4-dimethoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid, prepared by the condensation of 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde with ethyl bromoacetate, is identical with the acid described by Perkin and Schiess (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 88, 162; Tiemann and Will, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2079); *trans*-2-methoxy- α -methylcinnamic acid, prepared by the condensation of 2-methoxybenzaldehyde with ethyl α -bromopropionate, is identical with the acid prepared by Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 81, 415).

In order to see whether Perkin's reaction on 2-methoxy-aldehydes always lead to the *trans*-acids and not the *cis*-acids, the aldehydes, e.g., 2-methoxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde, 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde, 2-naphthol methyl ether-1-aldehyde have been submitted to Perkin's reaction with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate and also with propionic anhydride and sodium propionate and in each case it has been found that the acids obtained are identical with the *trans*-methoxycinnamic acids, prepared by the condensation of the corresponding aldehydes with ethyl bromoacetate or ethyl α -bromopropionate.

The formation of *o*-coumaric acid thus seems to be characteristic of the 2-methoxy-aldehydes irrespective of any substituent in the phenyl nucleus. This has been further confirmed by studying the condensation of 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde with malonic acid which also leads to the *trans*-acid (m.p. 184°, mixed m.p. 184°).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl β -Hydroxy- β -(2-methoxy-5-methyl)phenylpropionate.—A mixture of 2-methoxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde (8 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (13.4 g.), zinc wool (5.5 g.) and dry benzene (75 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath for 2½ hours when the zinc dissolved. The solution was poured into ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, the benzene layer separated, washed with sodium carbonate solution and then with water and dried. On removing benzene it was distilled at 200°/12 mm. as a colourless oil, yield 5.5 g.

Ethyl 2-Methoxy-5-methyl-trans-cinnamate.—The above compound (5.5 g.) was converted into the unsaturated ester with thionyl chloride (3 g.) in presence of pyridine (3 g.) in dry ethereal solution (100 c.c.). The ethereal layer after decomposition of the excess of thionyl chloride with powdered ice, was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, sodium carbonate and finally with water. On removing ether the product was distilled at 165°/7 mm., yield 3.8 g. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 7.4. C₁₃H₁₆O₃ requires C, 71.0; H, 7.27 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-methyl-trans-cinnamic Acid.—(a) The above unsaturated ester (1 g.) was hydrolysed by means of alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The acid was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 145-46°. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 6.3. C₁₁H₁₄O₃ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.7 per cent).

(b) *By Perkin's reaction.*—2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (2 g.) and fused sodium acetate (8 g.) at 180° for 10 hours. Dilute alkali was added to the mixture and the filtered solution acidified by hydrochloric acid, when the acid separated out which was crystallised from dilute alcohol, yield 7 g., m.p. 144-45° (mixed m.p. with the compound prepared above).

Demethylation of Ethyl 2-Methoxy-5-methyl-trans-cinnamate and 2-Methoxy-5-methyl-cinnamic Acid.—The ester or the acid was heated with hydriodic acid (sp. gr. 1.7) on a glycerine bath at 140° for 2 hours. The mixture was treated with powdered ice and then with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with cold dilute sodium carbonate solution. The ethereal solution was then kept for some time with cold dilute alkali and then washed with water. The ether was evaporated off, when there was no residue. The sodium carbonate and alkali washings on acidification gave a sticky precipitate, which, however, could not be crystallised.

The other compounds have been prepared in a similar manner and are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Name of the compound.	Prepared from	Molecular formula.	M.p. or b.p.	Analysis		Remarks.
				Found, C, H,	Calc. C, H,	
(1) Ethyl α -methyl- β -methylcinnamate	2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde + ethyl bromoacetate + zinc wool and the resulting hydroxy ester dehydrated with SOCl_2 + pyridine	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$	B.p. $160^\circ/5$ mm.	71.83 7.92	71.79 7.69	Colourless liquid
(2) α -Methyl- β -methyl- <i>trans</i> -cinnamic acid	Hydrolysis of (1)	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	M.p. $109-10^\circ$	70.0 6.8	70.65 7.4	Crystallised from spirit
"	2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde + sodium propionate and propionic anhydride (Perkin's reaction)		M.p. $109-10^\circ$ (mixed m.p.)			
(3) Ethyl 2:4-dimethoxycinnamate	2:4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde + ethyl bromoacetate and the hydroxy-ester dehydrated with SOCl_2 + pyridine.	...	B.p. $160^\circ/6$ mm.	...	...	Brown viscous liquid (cf. Chakravarti and Majumdar, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1940, 18, 350)
(4) 2:4-Dimethoxy- <i>trans</i> -cinnamic acid	Hydrolysis of (3)	...	M.p. 184°	...	...	...
"	Perkin's reaction from 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde.		"			
"	2:4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde + malonic acid + piperidine		"			
(5) Ethyl 2:4-dimethoxy- α -methylcinnamate	2:4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde + ethyl α -bromopropionate and the hydroxy-ester dehydrated with SOCl_2 + pyridine	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$	B.p. $200^\circ/6$ mm.	67.5 7.26	67.2 7.2	Viscous brown liquid
(6) 2:4-Dimethoxy- α -methyl- <i>trans</i> -cinnamic acid	Hydrolysis of (5)	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	M.p. 130°	65.0 6.1	64.86 6.3	Crystallised from alcohol
"	2:4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde + sodium propionate + propionic anhydride (Perkin's reaction)		M.p. 130° (mixed m.p.)			
(7) Ethyl β -(2-methoxy)-1-naphthyl acrylate	2-Naphthol methyl ether-1-aldehyde + ethyl bromoacetate and the hydroxy-ester dehydrated	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$	B.p. $210-12^\circ/4$ mm.	75.5 6.5	75.0 6.3	...
(8) β -(2-Methoxy)-1-naphthyl acrylic acid	Hydrolysis of (7)	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$	M.p. $153-54^\circ$	74.2 5.7	73.7 5.3	"
"	2-Naphthol methyl ether-1-aldehyde + sodium acetate + acetic anhydride (Perkin's reaction)		M.p. 153° (mixed m.p.)			
(9) Ethyl α -methyl- β -(2-methoxy)-1-naphthyl acrylate	2-Naphthol methyl ether-1-aldehyde + ethyl α -bromopropionate and the hydroxy-ester dehydrated	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$	B.p. $220-25^\circ/5$ mm.	75.8 6.6	75.5 6.6	Viscous brown liquid
(10) α -Methyl- β -(2-methoxy)-1-naphthyl acrylic acid	Hydrolysis of (9)	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$	M.p. $138-139^\circ$	74.0 5.9	74.39 5.8	Crystallised from alcohol
"	2-Naphthol methyl ether-1-aldehyde + sodium propionate + propionic anhydride (Perkin's reaction)		M.p. $138-39^\circ$ (mixed m.p.)			